

Pros and Cons of M-Commerce

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Abstract

Mobile commerce (also known as Mobile e-commerce or m-commerce) is a new trend for online shopping that uses wireless devices such as mobile phones for online transactions including online shopping, bill payments, etc. As the mobile developers are releasing interesting and useful apps every day, the use of mobile phones and tablets is increasing at a rapid pace. This induces mobile users to use their mobile devices for online payments and other transactions. This paper introduces the process of online transactions using mobile phones, its benefits, and counterparts as well as the level of adoption of the m-commerce by the people. At the conclusion, it also explores the future opportunities and the challenges for the m-commerce.

Introduction

The word m-commerce is derived from the widely used e-commerce which is an acronym for Electronic Commerce. After the great acceptance of e-commerce, the mobile commerce has become handier for the users. The mobile does not remain the device that is used only for making calls and all that simple utilities but it is a magical gadget that can help you pay your bills, purchase products and services online and so on. The scope of mobile commerce is far broad than that of e-commerce as the smart phones have become very common for the public. Performing online transactions using e-commerce requires the person to sit at a proper place to operate the computer. Whereas the m-commerce requires just a smart phone with Internet or Wi-Fi connectivity and the online transaction is just fun. The usage of m-commerce has been increased due to the availability and ease of use of mobile across the globe.

Pros and Cons of M-Commerce

M-commerce seems attractive and convenient at first glance, however; everything comes with several advantages and disadvantages, both. It is important to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of m-commerce for consumers as well as companies. Some of the major advantages of m-commerce include the convenience of use, reduce costs and increases personalization. On the other hand, some of the major disadvantages of technology include the small screen size of phones; apps are to be developed for each platform.

Advantages of M-commerce

M-commerce has been very popular in recent years majorly because of advancements in technologies and convenience of usage. The convenience of using smart phones to place orders online is a major factor working in favor of m-commerce. There is a large proportion of the population using smart phones daily, especially in developed and developing countries. People can use mobile phones at every place to use the services of e-commerce websites through the application provided by them. Majority of e-commerce giants have launched their mobile applications for the convenience of users. M-commerce is also cost-friendly for users because mobile internet is generally cheaper as compared to internet services being used at laptops or computer through Wi-Fi connectivity or dongles etc. M-commerce also increases personalization of shopping as. Generally, people can use their phone to utilize m-commerce facility. Like the usage of Facebook and Gmail, users can shop through their mobile phones.

Disadvantages of M-Commerce

Smaller screen size and security concern generally lead consumers to opt for e-commerce over m-commerce. The screen size of smart phones is being increased by makers, but it is sometimes inconvenient for users to analyze products from photos seen on small screens. Disadvantage or the extra burden to be handled by companies include the fact that there is a wide range of platforms in smartphones. Companies have to develop applications for all the platforms to cover the market properly. Another major issue for consumers is the high probability of fraud. “Any one, good or bad, can easily start a business. And there are many bad sites which eat up customers’ money. There is no guarantee of product quality. Mechanical failures can cause unpredictable effects on the total processes. As there is the minimum chance of direct customer to company interactions, customer loyalty is always on a check.”

Future Perspectives

After looking at various aspects regarding m-commerce and analyzing various pros and cons of m-commerce, it is important to see future perspectives of m-commerce. Advantages of m-commerce are expected to surpass the disadvantages and it is expected that m-commerce will be widely used for shopping, mobile recharges and DTH recharges, etc. Technology is in the initial phase and work is in progress to make transactions more secure. Smarts phones are very popular and are gaining much more popularity day by day. The convenience of “any time anywhere use” is the greatest strength of m-commerce and people are accepting this innovative way of shopping.

Conclusion

M-commerce is the latest way of shopping being popular among the large population. There are various advantages of m-commerce that are helping companies to adopt this route; also the convenience of its usage is attracting consumers. However, there are certain challenges to be faced by companies in convincing consumers about m-commerce’s advantages and convenience. Overall, the convenience of m-commerce is expected to surpass its little disadvantages and in future, m-commerce is expected to become much more popular.

Web Sources

<http://ijiet.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/46.pdf>

<http://www.esalestrack.com/blog/2008/09/advantages-and-disadvantages-of.html>

<http://www.careerindia.com/colleges/selvamm-arts-and-science-college-namakkal-tamil-nadu-cp4133/>